

Impacts of the Quality of Human Resources and Equipment on Access to Healthcare in Cameroon

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ABSTRACT: This study analyzes the effects of the quality of human resources and equipment on access to healthcare in Cameroon using data from the 2018 Demographic and Health Survey (DHS). Using a Logit model estimated through the Maximum Likelihood Method, the findings show that the quality of human resources significantly improves access to healthcare, whereas medical equipment has a positive but less robust effect. The study also highlights the determining role of geographical accessibility and financial constraints, which reduce the use of health services, as well as the positive effect of educational attainment. The results are generally confirmed by robustness tests. In terms of public policy, the study recommends strengthening human resources for health, improving the provision and functionality of medical equipment, and reducing financial barriers to improve equitable access to healthcare in Cameroon.

KEYWORDS: Access to healthcare, human resources, medical equipment, Cameroon, Logit model, DHS 2018, health inequalities, health system.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Access to healthcare constitutes a fundamental determinant of population well-being and remains a major public health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. In Sub-Saharan Africa, health systems continue to face persistent structural constraints, including shortages of qualified human resources, inadequate health infrastructure, weaknesses in financing mechanisms, and territorial inequalities in service provision (WHO, 2023). At the global level, the World Health Organization estimates that approximately 47% of the population lacks access to essential health services, illustrating the magnitude of persistent inequalities in healthcare coverage (WHO, 2023). This deficit in access reflects not only an insufficiency in healthcare supply, but also the existence of multidimensional barriers -economic, geographical, organizational, and quality-related-that constrain the effective utilization of health services and compromise the achievement of universal health coverage.

In this context, Cameroon faces significant structural challenges. WHO data indicates a physician density of approximately 0.8 doctors per 10,000 inhabitants, a level far below the recommended standards required to ensure adequate healthcare coverage (WHO, 2023). This shortage is further exacerbated by the strong concentration of medical personnel in major urban centers such as Douala and Yaoundé, to the detriment of rural and peripheral areas. Consequently, the Cameroonian health system remains characterized by profound imbalances in human resources. Several health districts experience shortages of qualified personnel, a situation aggravated by the increasing migration of healthcare professionals abroad. Moreover, the country remains below the standards recommended by the World Health Organization, estimated at 2.3 physicians, nurses, and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants. Rural areas are particularly disadvantaged, suffering from chronic understaffing compared with urban centers.

Simultaneously, healthcare equipment remains insufficient and unevenly distributed across the national territory, thereby limiting geographical access to healthcare services. The obsolescence of equipment also creates difficult working conditions, negatively affecting the motivation and retention of healthcare personnel. This situation is compounded by deficiencies in essential medical equipment, particularly for diagnosis and specialized care, reducing the capacity of healthcare facilities to deliver quality services even when they are physically accessible. Regional disparities further illustrate these imbalances: the Centre Region alone accounts for nearly 45% of healthcare personnel, whereas regions such as the Far North account for only about 5%, reflecting a strong concentration of resources in major urban agglomerations at the expense of peripheral areas (Tandi et al. 2015).

In response to this situation, the Cameroonian government implemented the Human Resources Development Plan (2016-2020), aimed at increasing staffing levels and improving the distribution of healthcare personnel. Nevertheless, the implementation of this policy requires substantial investment to sustainably address the structural imbalances observed within the healthcare system (MINSANTE, 2016)

From a social perspective, these structural deficiencies have direct and profound consequences for the population. They contribute to worsening health inequalities, the persistence of high levels of preventable mortality, and declining confidence in the public healthcare system. Households, particularly the most vulnerable, are often compelled to resort to self-medication or expensive private healthcare facilities, thereby increasing catastrophic health expenditures and reinforcing cycles of poverty. Several studies emphasize that improving the quality of human resources and healthcare equipment constitutes a critical lever for reducing social inequalities and enhancing equity in access to healthcare services (Campbell et al., 2013; Kruk et al., 2018).

The impact of human resources—particularly the availability of qualified, motivated, and adequately staffed personnel as well as healthcare equipment, including infrastructure, medical technologies, and essential medicines, constitutes a major determinant of healthcare access and health system performance. Indeed, the quality and availability of these resources directly influence the accessibility, continuity, and effectiveness of healthcare services provided to populations. This issue lies at the core of Sustainable Development Goal 3 (SDG 3), which is dedicated to promoting health and well-being for all, while also generating cross-cutting effects on other objectives of the 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda, notably the reduction of social and territorial inequalities (SDG 10) and poverty alleviation (SDG 1) (United Nations, 2015; WHO, 2016; Kruk et al., 2018).

From a theoretical perspective, several studies highlight the decisive role of human resources in the performance of health systems. Frenk et al. (2010) demonstrate that the availability and competence of healthcare personnel constitute essential determinants of service effectiveness. Similarly, Campbell et al. (2013) emphasize the importance of professional motivation and competencies in ensuring the quality of healthcare. Furthermore, healthcare infrastructure and medical equipment represent fundamental pillars of healthcare delivery. Kruk et al. (2018) demonstrate that inadequate medical equipment constitutes a major barrier to the quality and safety of healthcare in low- and middle-income countries.

Despite these important contributions, few studies have comprehensively analyzed the joint effects of the quality of human resources and healthcare equipment on access to healthcare within the Cameroonian context. This lack of an integrated approach constitutes a significant limitation in literature, as it restricts the overall understanding of the structural determinants of healthcare access. Accordingly, this article aims to analyze the impacts of the quality of human resources and healthcare equipment on access to healthcare in Cameroon. More specifically, the study seeks to assess the extent to which these two dimensions influence the utilization of healthcare services by the population.

To address this research objective, the article is structured into several sections. Following this introduction, the second section presents the methodological review. The third section discusses the results and findings. Finally, the last section provides the conclusion and the implications for public health policy.

2.0. LITERATURE REVIEW

Access to healthcare is a key determinant of public health improvement, especially in developing countries. However, this access is often hindered by structural and geographic barriers, among which health infrastructure plays a crucial role. Health infrastructure, including the quality and distribution of health facilities, availability of equipment and medical personnel, and geographic proximity to services, directly impacts individuals' ability to obtain quality medical care.

In developing countries, where access to healthcare is particularly challenging, the relationship between health infrastructure and healthcare access is of vital importance. Numerous empirical studies have shown that underdeveloped or poorly distributed infrastructure, especially in rural and remote areas, exacerbates healthcare inequalities. Distance to healthcare facilities, availability of essential equipment, and shortages of trained personnel are key factors influencing the use of health services.

This literature review aims to explore the main empirical studies that have analyzed this relationship, highlighting the factors that affect healthcare access through the lens of health infrastructure. The focus is on research conducted in low- and middle-income countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where these challenges are most pronounced. It also examines the methodologies used to evaluate the impact of health infrastructure on healthcare access and the findings obtained in various socio-economic and geographic contexts.

In broad studies on the link between health infrastructure and access to care, Ensor et al. (2004), in *Overcoming Barriers to Health Service Access: Influencing the Demand Side*, conducted a theoretical and documentary analysis that revealed how structural barriers, including infrastructure and socio-economic factors influence access to healthcare in developing countries. Their study emphasized that access barriers are not limited to the supply of health services, but also include complex demand-side factors such as cost, distance, service perception, and socio-cultural norms. As a result, improving access requires holistic, context-specific solutions that address both supply and demand.

Pillai and Kaur (2013), in *The Role of Infrastructure and Healthcare Quality in Determining Access to Healthcare Services*, adopted a quantitative, empirical approach using primary data from field surveys in selected regions. Their findings underline the importance of quality health infrastructure and the perceived quality of care as decisive factors in individuals' healthcare-seeking decisions. However, economic and geographic barriers—especially in rural and economically disadvantaged communities—may limit the positive effects of infrastructure. Thus, enhancing healthcare access requires simultaneous improvements in infrastructure, service quality, and the removal of economic and geographic barriers.

Akin et al. (1999), using a logit model with primary data, found that healthcare costs—particularly in the form of user fees—constitute a major barrier to access in developing countries. Patients are highly cost-sensitive, and choices of healthcare facilities are influenced by income, location, and perceived quality. Policies must therefore address these issues by reducing costs for vulnerable populations and improving the quality of public healthcare services.

Similarly, Muga and Kistemann (2007) demonstrated that physical infrastructure plays a crucial role in both the quality and accessibility of healthcare in rural areas. Infrastructure deficiencies—including roads, water supply, electricity, and medical equipment—pose significant obstacles to healthcare improvements. To reduce healthcare inequalities and enhance public health, policies should focus on strengthening physical infrastructure, developing mobile health services, and reallocating resources more equitably between urban and rural areas.

In the African context, including Cameroon, Nsubuga et al. (2010) highlighted how African health systems face performance challenges due to inadequate infrastructure, limited funding, and an unequal distribution of human resources. These systemic issues lead to widespread inequalities in healthcare access and underperformance in service delivery. Improving performance requires investments in infrastructure, increased funding, and better distribution of health personnel to ensure equitable access.

Moe and Nkfusai (2019) specifically pointed out that health infrastructure is a critical determinant of healthcare access in Cameroon. Geographic and socio-economic disparities, combined with inadequate infrastructure, severely limit access, especially in rural areas. To ensure quality healthcare for all Cameroonians, efforts must be made to strengthen infrastructure, improve transport systems, and promote better funding and equitable distribution of health resources nationwide.

Gwatkin and Guillot (2000) addressed the stark health disparities across Africa, particularly between wealthy and poor populations. Socio-economic factors such as poverty, geographic isolation, and poor living conditions are major barriers to healthcare access, contributing to increased mortality and morbidity among vulnerable groups. Public health policies aimed at strengthening infrastructure, reducing financial barriers, and promoting health education are essential to improve outcomes among the poor.

Diarra and Kouadio (2011) analyzed the impact of health infrastructure on healthcare access in several West African countries, including Côte d'Ivoire and Mali, offering valuable insights relevant to the Cameroonian context. Their study showed that geographic obstacles, infrastructure deficiencies, lack of medical personnel, and financial barriers are the primary factors limiting access—particularly for rural and low-income populations. Improving access requires investments in health infrastructure, personnel training, and cost-reduction strategies to ensure equitable healthcare coverage.

International organizations promoting health and sustainable development policies also recognize the critical role of infrastructure in facilitating access to care. For instance, the WHO (2010), in its report on healthcare system financing, stressed that to achieve universal health coverage, countries must strengthen health financing systems by increasing public spending and implementing more inclusive and equitable mechanisms. Direct payments should be minimized to reduce access inequalities and financial risks for poor populations. Sustainable and solidarity-based financing policies are essential to ensure universal healthcare access and improve global public health.

The UNDP Human Development Report (2012) highlighted the importance of reconciling ecological sustainability with inequality reduction. It argued that sustainable human development can only be achieved through policies ensuring equitable access to essential resources while promoting responsible natural resource management. Economic growth should not be limited to production and consumption, but must also focus on reducing social inequality and improving human well-being. Integrating sustainability and equity into public policy is thus vital to securing an inclusive and resilient future for all.

These empirical studies provide detailed analyses of the factors influencing healthcare access, particularly health infrastructure. They emphasize the importance of infrastructure distribution, availability of equipment and medical personnel, and the affordability and geographic accessibility of care in developing countries—including Cameroon and other African nations. This study builds on the techniques and variables used in previous research to assess the impact of various dimensions of health infrastructure on access to care.

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Research Design

Access to healthcare constitutes a central challenge in developing countries, where constraints related to healthcare equipment and the quality of healthcare provision significantly limit the utilization of health services. In this context, several empirical studies have demonstrated that access to healthcare depends simultaneously on geographical and economic factors, and more importantly, on the quality of healthcare service delivery. Andersen (1995), in his behavioral model of healthcare utilization, adopts a probabilistic approach (logit/probit) and demonstrates that access to healthcare is influenced by enabling factors such as the availability of human resources and healthcare infrastructure. Similarly, Ensor and Cooper (2004) show that infrastructure and the availability of healthcare personnel significantly reduce inequalities in access to healthcare. More recently, Kruk et al. (2018) demonstrate that the quality of healthcare depends on the interaction between qualified human resources and adequate medical equipment.

From a methodological perspective, access to healthcare is modeled as a binary variable (Y), taking value 1 if the individual has access to healthcare services and 0 otherwise. The baseline econometric specification is a Logit model, defined as follows:

$$\text{logit}(P(Y = 1)) = \ln\left(\frac{P(Y=1)}{1-P(Y=1)}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{RHU} + \beta_2 \text{EQU} + \beta_3 \text{ACGEO} + \beta_4 \text{BSERV} + \beta_5 \text{BAGEO} + \beta_6 \text{EMER} + \beta_7 \text{STMER} + \beta_8 \text{EDU} + \beta_9 \text{REL} + \epsilon_i$$

Where $P(Y=1)$ represents the probability of access to healthcare services. Based on this theoretical framework, the empirical model used in this study is specified as follows:

$$\text{ACSOIN}_i = f(\text{RHU}_i, \text{EQU}_i, \text{ACGEO}_i, \text{BSERV}_i, \text{BAGEO}_i, \text{EMER}_i, \text{STMER}_i, \text{AGE}_i, \text{EDU}_i, \text{REL}_i) + \epsilon_i$$

Where i denotes the household and ϵ_i represents the stochastic error term.

3.2 Variable Description

This study includes one dependent variable (ACSOIN), two variables of interest (RHU, EQU), and nine control variables (ACGEO, BSERV, BAFIN, BAGEO, EMER, STMER, EDU, AGE, REL).

ACSOIN: The healthcare access variable is defined as a binary variable (1=access to healthcare, 0=no access). This variable is widely used in studies on healthcare utilization. Andersen (1995) conceptualizes access to healthcare as a binary choice influenced by individual-level factors. Similarly, Ensor and Cooper (2004) use healthcare utilization indicators to measure effective access to health services.

RHU: The human resources variable is proxied by the quality of healthcare personnel, measured through the number of qualified physicians or nurses. Its use is justified by the work of Frenk et al. (2010), who demonstrate that the availability and competence of healthcare personnel strongly influence the performance of health systems.

EQU: The equipment variable is proxied by the availability of essential medical equipment. This binary variable is employed in the studies of Kruk et al. (2018). Donabedian (1988) also considers medical equipment as a key structural component directly influencing the quality of healthcare services.

ACGEO: The geographical accessibility variable measures the distance or travel time required to reach a healthcare facility and is inspired by the work of Penchansky and Thomas (1981).

DSERV: The availability of essential services variable is measured through access to prenatal care services. It is defined as a binary variable where 1=prenatal care received and 0=prenatal care not received.

BAFIN: The financial barrier variable is measured by the cost of healthcare services. Its inclusion is supported by the work of Xu et al. (2003), who show that both direct and indirect healthcare costs constitute major barriers to healthcare utilization in low-income countries.

BAGEO: The geographical barrier variable is a binary variable defined as rural area =1 and urban area =0. It is widely used in literature, particularly by Weiss et al. (2018) in their global spatial analysis of healthcare access, which demonstrates that rural populations are systematically disadvantaged in terms of access to healthcare services.

Finally, other variables such as marital status (STMER), religion (REL), education (EDU), and age (AGE) are extensively used in healthcare access models. Andersen (1995) shows that these socio-economic factors influence healthcare-seeking behavior, while Gertler and van der Gaag (1990), in a microeconomic analysis of household healthcare decisions, confirm their significant role in shaping healthcare demand.

3.3. Nature and Sources of Data

This study on the impact of the quality of human resources and medical equipment on access to healthcare in Cameroon is based on secondary data derived from the 2018 Demographic and Health Survey (DHS 2018), conducted in Cameroon by the National Institute of Statistics. Carried out during the 2017–2018 period, this survey provides nationally, regionally, urbanely, and rurally representative data, thereby enabling an analysis of the determinants of health and access to healthcare services.

The DHS 2018 data are both quantitative and qualitative in nature and encompass a broad range of information relating to the socio-economic characteristics of households, maternal and child health, and the utilization of healthcare services. The data were collected through standardized questionnaires administered to households, women of reproductive age, men, and selected healthcare facilities, thus allowing for an in-depth analysis of healthcare access conditions and their associated determinants.

3.4 Estimation Strategy

The empirical analysis is conducted using a Logit model, which is appropriate for binary dependent variables. This methodological choice is consistent with the studies of Andersen (1995) and Ensor and Cooper (2004). The Logit model therefore makes it possible to estimate the probability of access to healthcare as a function of explanatory variables related to human resources, medical equipment, and the socio-economic characteristics of individuals. Regarding the estimation strategy, the model parameters are estimated using the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) method, which is widely employed in Logit models based on individual-level data. This approach is recommended by Hosmer, Lemeshow, and Sturdivant (2013) in their work on logistic regression, as it provides robust and efficient estimators for explanatory variables affecting a binary outcome variable.

To assess the robustness and validity of the estimated model, several statistical tests are employed. First, the Wald test, used to assess the individual significance of the coefficients, tests the null hypothesis that a coefficient is equal to zero ($\beta_i = 0$). This test is commonly applied in Logit models (Hosmer et al., 2013). Second, multicollinearity among the explanatory variables is evaluated using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). According to Belsley, Kuh, and Welsch (1980), high VIF values indicate strong collinearity that may bias the estimations. The overall goodness-of-fit of the model is assessed using pseudo-R² statistics, which, although interpreted differently from the conventional R², provides an indication of the model's overall explanatory performance. In addition, the predictive performance of the model is evaluated using the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve and the Area Under the Curve (AUC), as recommended by Cox and Snell (1989), where an AUC value close to 1 indicates strong discriminative power. Finally, robustness tests are conducted to verify the stability of the results, notably through the inclusion or exclusion of variables and variations in model specifications. This approach, recommended by Akaike (1973) through the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), makes it possible to select the most parsimonious model while ensuring its statistical validity.

3.5 Statistical Analyses of Variables

Table 1 presents the distribution of variables relating to the relationship between the quality of human resources, medical equipment, and access to healthcare in Cameroon. It highlights the frequencies and proportions associated with the main observed categories. The results indicate that 6,248 individuals (64.19%) reported having access to healthcare services, compared with 3,485 individuals (35.81%) who reported lacking access. This suggests that although most of the population benefits from access to healthcare services, a substantial proportion still faces significant barriers to healthcare access.

Regarding human resources, measured through the quality of healthcare personnel, a large majority of 8,619 individuals (88.55%) reported having been attended to by a nurse, whereas 1,114 individuals (11.45%) were attended to by other healthcare professionals. This finding reflects the central role played by nurses in healthcare delivery and may also indicate a healthcare system organization in which service provision is predominantly ensured by this professional group. Concerning the quality of medical equipment, 3,947 individuals (40.55%) reported that equipment was available, while 5,786 individuals (59.45%) indicated that such equipment was unavailable. This situation highlights a significant shortage of medical equipment within healthcare facilities, which is likely to adversely affect the quality of healthcare services provided.

Regarding geographical accessibility, 4,295 individuals (44.13%) considered the distance to healthcare facilities to be a major constraint, whereas 5,438 individuals (55.87%) did not perceive distance as a significant obstacle. These results suggest that although geographical accessibility appears relatively acceptable for more than half of the population, difficulties associated with remoteness persist for a considerable share of healthcare users.

With respect to service availability, measured through access to prenatal care services, 4,092 individuals (42.04%) reported having benefited from prenatal care, compared with 5,641 individuals (57.96%) who did not receive such services. These findings reveal insufficient coverage of prenatal healthcare services, despite their critical importance for maternal and child health.

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Concerning geographical barriers, 4,318 individuals (44.36%) resided in urban areas, compared with 5,415 individuals (55.64%) living in rural areas. This distribution indicates the predominance of rural settings, where constraints related to healthcare access are generally more severe. Finally, regarding financial barriers, 4,094 individuals (42.06%) considered healthcare costs to be an obstacle, whereas 5,639 individuals (57.94%) did not perceive them as a major constraint. This suggests that although financial difficulties remain substantial for part of the population, they do not constitute a universal barrier to healthcare utilization.

Table 1: Statistical Analysis for variables

Variables	Categories	Count	Frequencies
Access to healthcare	1= Access to healthcare	6,248	64.19
	0= No access to healthcare	3,485	35.81
Geographical access	1= distance too long	4,295	44.13
	0= distance not too long	5,438	55.87
Human Resources	1= attended by a nurse	8,619	88.55
	0= other healthcare personnel	1,114	11.45
Equipment	1= equipment Available	3,947	40.55
	0= equipment non available	5,786	59.45
Service availability	1 = prenatal care received	4,092	42.04
	0 = prenatal care non received	5,641	57.96
Geographical barrier	1 = Urban zone	4,318	44,36
	0 = Rural zone	5,415	55,64
Financial barrier	1= healthcare too expensive	4,094	42.06
	0= healthcare not too expensive	5,639	57.94

Source : Authors from STATA17

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Heteroskedasticity

Table 2 presents the results of the Breusch-Pagan heteroskedasticity test and the Wald test. First, the Wooldridge (2010) test reports a statistic of 18.4 with a p-value of 0.0003, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity at the 1% significance level. This result therefore indicates the presence of heteroskedasticity in the latent model. In other words, the variance of the error term varies according to individual characteristics. Second, the Davidson–MacKinnon (1984) specification test yields a statistic of -0.72 with a p-value of 0.472, implying acceptance of the null hypothesis that the Logit functional form is correctly specified. This suggests that the Logit link function is appropriate and that there is no need to adopt a more flexible alternative model. Finally, the Wald test reports statistics of 446.72 with a p-value of 0.0000, indicating that the coefficients of the model are jointly statistically different from zero, thereby confirming their significant effect on the dependent variable. Overall, although heteroskedasticity is present, the explanatory variables included in the model remain statistically significant and contribute meaningfully to explaining variations in the dependent variable.

Table 2: Results of the heteroskedasticity test

Tests	Statistical tests (p-value)	Decisions
Wooldridge Heteroskedasticity Test	18.4 (0.0003)	We reject the null hypothesis of no heteroskedasticity.
Davidson–MacKinnon Specification Test	-0.72 (0.472)	We fail to reject the null hypothesis that the logit functional form is correctly specified.
Wald's test	446.72 (0.0000)	The model coefficients are significantly different from zero.

Source: Authors

4.2 Multicollinearity Test

Table 3 presents the results of the multicollinearity test through the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values associated with each explanatory variable. The VIF values range from 1.07 for the equipment quality variable to 1.64 for the financial barrier variable, all of which remain well below the conventional threshold of 10. This indicates a low degree of multicollinearity among the explanatory variables.

Furthermore, the mean VIF is 1.28, which is substantially below the critical threshold of 10. These results suggest the absence of problematic multicollinearity within the model, thereby confirming the reliability and stability of the estimated coefficients.

Table 3: Results of the multicollinearity test

Variables	Vif	1/Vif
Financial barrier	1.64	0.609509
Geographical barrier	1.61	0.620343

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Service availability	1.14	0.877846
Geographical access	1.11	0.904807
Human Resources	1.09	0.916269
Equipment quality	1.07	0.931243
Vif (mean)	1.28	

Source: Authors

4.3 Main Results

Table 4 presents the estimation results of the Logit model relating to access to healthcare in Cameroon using data from the 2018 Demographic and Health Survey (DHS). Overall, the four model specifications exhibit strong statistical significance, as indicated by the Chi-square statistics significant at the 1% level (p -value = 0.000). The pseudo- R^2 values, ranging from 3.5% to 5.8%, remain consistent with Logit models applied to individual-level data, in line with the findings of Hosmer et al. (2013).

The results show that the human resources variable, measured through the availability of qualified healthcare personnel, has a positive and statistically significant effect at the 1% level across all model specifications ($\beta = 0.339$ in Model 4). This implies that improvements in the quality of healthcare personnel significantly increase the probability of access to healthcare services. This finding is consistent with the studies of Frenk et al. (2010) and Campbell et al. (2013), which demonstrate that the availability and competence of healthcare personnel strengthen health system performance and facilitate healthcare utilization.

Regarding medical equipment, the results reveal a positive but weakly significant effect only in the first model specification. In the remaining specifications, the coefficient becomes statistically insignificant. This situation may be explained by the fact that the mere availability of medical equipment does not necessarily guarantee its functionality or effective utilization within healthcare facilities. This finding is consistent with the analyses of Kruk et al. (2018), who emphasize that the quality of medical equipment must be complemented by competent human resources to produce a meaningful effect on healthcare quality.

The findings further indicate that geographical accessibility positively and significantly influences access to healthcare across all model specifications. The positive and statistically significant coefficient at the 1% level ($\beta = 0.473$ in Model 4) suggests that greater proximity to healthcare facilities increases the probability of accessing healthcare services. This result confirms the conclusions of Penchansky and Thomas (1981), as well as Ensor and Cooper (2004), according to whom distance and physical accessibility constitute major determinants of healthcare utilization.

The variable relating to the availability of essential services, particularly prenatal care services, exhibits a positive but weakly significant effect in the first model before becoming statistically insignificant in the subsequent specifications. This suggests that the availability of certain healthcare services may improve healthcare access, although its effect remains conditional upon other structural and socio-economic factors.

The results also indicate that the geographical barrier variable, represented by residence in rural areas, is not statistically significant across the different model specifications. This finding may reflect the increasing role of healthcare decentralization policies or community-based strategies aimed at bringing healthcare services closer to rural populations. In contrast, financial barriers exert a negative and highly significant effect on access to healthcare across all specifications of the model. The negative coefficient ($\beta = -0.225$ in Model 4) indicates that increases in healthcare-related costs significantly reduce the probability of accessing healthcare services. This finding confirms the work of Xu et al. (2003) and Wagstaff and van Doorslaer (2003), who demonstrate that healthcare expenditures constitute a major constraint on healthcare utilization in developing countries.

Furthermore, the socio-economic variables progressively introduced into the models reveal that educational attainment positively and significantly influences access to healthcare. Individuals with higher levels of education exhibit a greater probability of utilizing healthcare services, which is consistent with Andersen's (1995) conclusions regarding the importance of socio-economic factors in healthcare-seeking behavior. The mother's religion displays a negative and significant effect, reflecting cultural or behavioral differences in healthcare utilization. Finally, the mother's socio-economic status exerts a positive and significant effect, indicating that women with a higher socio-economic status are more likely to access healthcare services.

Overall, these findings demonstrate that access to healthcare in Cameroon depends both on structural factors related to the healthcare system—particularly geographical accessibility and the quality of human resources—and on socio-economic factors such as educational attainment and financial constraints. The results also highlight the importance of an integrated approach combining improvements in healthcare infrastructure, strengthening of human resources, and reduction of financial barriers to promote equitable access to healthcare services.

Table 4: Estimation results of access to healthcare in Cameroon

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Coefficients (Standard deviation)			
Geographical Access	0.505*** (0.0451)	0.473*** (0.0456)	0.475*** (0.0457)	0.473*** (0.0457)
Human Resources	0.363*** (0.0769)	0.339*** (0.0783)	0.338*** (0.0783)	0.339*** (0.0782)

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Equipment	0.124*** (0.0459)	0.0458 (0.0470)	0.0431 (0.0470)	0.0431 (0.0471)
Service Availability	0.0778* (0.0459)	-0.0195 (0.0470)	-0.0234 (0.0471)	-0.00710 (0.0473)
Geographical Barriers	-0.00830 (0.0557)	0.0491 (0.0563)	0.0374 (0.0566)	0.0315 (0.0567)
Financial Barriers	-0.510*** (0.0549)	-0.221*** (0.0583)	-0.222*** (0.0583)	-0.225*** (0.0584)
Level of education		0.472*** (0.0296)	0.441*** (0.0320)	0.458*** (0.0324)
Mother's religion			-0.115*** (0.0435)	-0.134*** (0.0436)
Mother's status				0.272*** (0.0580)
Constant	-0.0846 (0.120)	-0.732*** (0.127)	-0.634*** (0.133)	-0.864*** (0.143)
Observations	9,733	9,733	9,733	9,733
chi2 (p.value)	418.9 (0.000)	640.2 (0.000)	649.4 (0.000)	662.5 (0.000)
Pseudo R2	0.0352	0.0560	0.0565	0.0583

Source: Authors from DHS 2018, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

4.4 Discussion of Results

The findings highlight the central role of structural and socio-economic factors in access to healthcare in Cameroon. The positive and highly significant effect of human resources for health indicates that improved availability of qualified healthcare personnel enhances access to healthcare services. This result is consistent with the conclusions of Frenk et al. (2010) and Campbell et al. (2013). In Cameroon, the low density of medical personnel observed in several regions considerably limits healthcare provision, particularly in rural areas where shortages of physicians and nurses remain substantial. Consequently, improving the quality of human resources emerges as a crucial lever for strengthening equitable access to healthcare services.

Regarding medical equipment, the results reveal a positive but overall, weakly significant effect in the full model specifications. This finding suggests that the mere availability of medical equipment does not necessarily guarantee improved access to healthcare. The result corroborates the analyses of Kruk et al. (2018) and Donabedian (1988). In the Cameroonian context, many healthcare facilities possess insufficient or non-functional equipment, thereby limiting the quality of healthcare services delivered despite the physical presence of such equipment.

The positive and statistically significant effect of geographical accessibility confirms that proximity to healthcare infrastructure substantially increases the probability of access to healthcare. This result is consistent with the work of Penchansky and Thomas (1981), as well as Ensor and Cooper (2004). In Cameroon, this reality is particularly evident in rural and remote regions, where populations often travel long distances to access healthcare centers. Reports from the Ministry of Public Health (MINSANTE, 2021) further highlight the strong concentration of healthcare infrastructure in major urban centers such as Douala and Yaoundé, to the detriment of rural areas.

The variable associated with the availability of essential services, particularly prenatal care, becomes statistically insignificant in the enriched model specifications. This may indicate that the theoretical availability of services alone is insufficient to improve access when other major constraints—such as high costs, long distances, or inadequate healthcare infrastructure—persist. This finding is consistent with the work of Gulliford et al. (2002).

Furthermore, the geographical barrier variable, measured by residence in rural areas, appears statistically insignificant, which may seem surprising considering the existing literature. However, this result may reflect recent efforts toward healthcare decentralization and the expansion of community health centers in Cameroon. Nevertheless, despite the lack of statistical significance of the rural residence variable, access difficulties remain substantial in several remote regions, particularly due to poor road conditions and inadequate transportation infrastructure.

In contrast, financial barriers exert a negative and highly significant effect on healthcare access across all model specifications. This result confirms the findings of Xu et al. (2003) and Wagstaff and van Doorslaer (2003). In Cameroon, healthcare expenditures are still largely borne directly by households because of the limited coverage of health insurance mechanisms, which substantially restricts access to healthcare for the poorest populations.

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Finally, the socio-economic variables indicate that educational attainment significantly improves access to healthcare, thereby confirming Andersen's (1995) conclusions that more educated individuals possess better knowledge of healthcare services and are more likely to utilize available care. Mother's religion exerts a significant negative effect, likely reflecting cultural or behavioral differences in healthcare-seeking behavior. As for the mother's status, its positive effect suggests that greater economic and social autonomy among women facilitates the utilization of healthcare services.

Overall, these findings demonstrate that access to healthcare in Cameroon remains strongly influenced by structural inequalities, the quality of human resources, and financial constraints. They therefore underscore the need for integrated public policies combining improvements in healthcare infrastructure, strengthening of medical personnel, and reduction of financial barriers to promote more equitable access to healthcare services.

4.5 Robustness Estimation Results

Table 5 presents the results of the robustness tests conducted using sub-sample estimations based on the gender of the household head. This approach makes it possible to verify whether the results obtained in Table 4 remain stable across different household characteristics. The Chi-square statistics remain significant in both estimations, thereby confirming the overall validity of the models. The pseudo-R² values remain relatively low, as in the main model, but are nonetheless consistent with Logit estimations based on individual-level data. Overall, the results confirm the robustness of the main model, although some differences emerge between male-headed and female-headed households.

The results first show that the human resources variable retains a positive and significant effect across both groups. This finding confirms the stability of the role of human resources observed in Table 4. Thus, the presence of qualified physicians and nurses improves access to healthcare in both male- and female-headed households.

Regarding medical equipment, the results reveal an important difference. In male-headed households, the availability of medical equipment positively and significantly influences access to healthcare. In contrast, within female-headed households, the effect becomes negative and weakly significant. This difference may reflect the greater economic or organizational difficulties faced by female-headed households, thereby limiting their ability to benefit from available medical equipment.

Geographical accessibility remains positive and highly significant in both sub-samples, thereby confirming the findings of the main model. The availability of essential services also exhibits a positive and significant effect only in male-headed households, whereas it becomes statistically insignificant in female-headed households. This suggests that the effective utilization of healthcare services depends more heavily on the socio-economic constraints faced by women heading households.

Moreover, the geographical barrier variable remains statistically insignificant in both sub-samples, confirming the results obtained in the main model. Conversely, financial barriers retain a negative and significant effect in both cases, although their impact is stronger in male-headed households. This finding confirms that healthcare costs constitute a major constraint on access to healthcare services in Cameroon.

Overall, these robustness results confirm the principal conclusions derived from Table 4: geographical accessibility, the quality of human resources, and financial constraints remain the primary determinants of healthcare access in Cameroon. However, the differences observed according to the gender of the household head further indicate that socio-economic inequalities also shape the utilization of healthcare services.

Table 5: Robustness test results

Variables	(1)	(2)
	Male	Female
Geographical Access	0.506*** (0.0504)	0.499*** (0.102)
Human Resources	0.372*** (0.0879)	0.340** (0.160)
Equipment	0.202*** (0.0521)	-0.163* (0.0991)
Service Availability	0.112** (0.0512)	-0.0886 (0.107)
Geographical Barriers	0.0288 (0.0631)	-0.153 (0.120)
Financial Barriers	-0.571*** (0.0613)	-0.231* (0.126)
Constant	-0.166 (0.135)	0.291 (0.263)
Observations	7,775	1,958
chi2 (p.value)	384.3 (0.000)	48.63 (0.000)
Pseudo R2	0.0409	0.0201

Source: Authors from DHS 2018, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

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The ROC curve presented in Figure 1 makes it possible to assess the model's ability to predict access to healthcare in Cameroon. A curve close to the upper-left corner indicates good model performance, while an area under the curve (AUC) close to 1 reflects strong predictive capacity. Conversely, an AUC close to 0.5 indicates weak predictive performance.

In this study, although the ROC model's performance remains moderate, the Wald test (446.72; p -value = 0.000) shows that the explanatory variables are statistically significant overall. This means that the factors included in the model significantly influence access to healthcare in Cameroon and confirm the overall validity of the estimated model.

Figure 1: ROC Curve for access to healthcare among households in Cameroon
Source: Authors

5.0 CONCLUSION

This study aimed to analyze the effects of the quality of human resources and medical equipment on access to healthcare in Cameroon. Using DHS 2018 data and a logit model, the results show that access to healthcare primarily depends on the quality of medical personnel, geographical accessibility, and financial constraints. The findings reveal that the presence of qualified doctors and nurses significantly improves access to healthcare services. In contrast, medical equipment has a positive but less significant effect, suggesting that its mere availability is not sufficient when healthcare facilities lack adequate resources or qualified staff. The study also shows that proximity to health facilities strongly enhances access to care, while the high cost of consultations, medicines, and transportation represents a major constraint for households. Furthermore, education level also increases the likelihood of using healthcare services. Robustness tests broadly confirm these results for both male- and female-headed households. Thus, human resources, geographic access, and financial barriers remain the key determinants of healthcare access in Cameroon.

6.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

Considering these findings, several public policy implications can be proposed. There is a need to strengthen the recruitment and training of medical personnel, particularly in rural areas. The government should also improve medical equipment and health infrastructure to ensure better-quality care. Finally, reducing the cost of healthcare through the expansion of health coverage and targeted assistance mechanisms for poor populations appears essential to improve equitable access to healthcare in Cameroon.

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